

Online Oral Presentation #6 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

AUTHORS

Burcu Erdogdu

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1334-1503>

Serpil Demirag

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8353-2843>

AFFILIATIONS

Aydin Adnan Menderes University
School of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Aydin, Turkey

Aydin Adnan Menderes University
School of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Aydin, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Communication tools have played a significant role in human life since ancient times. While phones were initially used solely for communication, they are now preferred for personal, social, and even professional purposes, facilitating daily life through various applications (Arslan, 2016; Yusufoglu, 2017). There is limited research on how this transformation in communication affects individuals' life satisfaction. This study aims to identify smartphone addiction among individuals visiting our units and determine the factors influencing life satisfaction, thereby raising awareness on this issue.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted with all volunteer patients, consecutively visited our department's facilities in a six-month-period. The survey form consists of three sections. The first section includes 36 questions addressing participants' sociodemographic characteristics, smartphone and internet usage, and factors affecting life satisfaction. The second section contains the 10-question Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short Form (SAS-SF), and the third section includes the 5-question Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS). A higher score on the SWLS indicates greater life satisfaction. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 25.1 software.

Results: The study included 363 participants with a mean age of 38.5 ± 12.8 years, 51% of whom were male. The daily smartphone usage time was 1-2 hours for 25.3% of participants and 3-4 hours for 37.2%. The mean total score on the Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short Form was 26.2 ± 12.1 (min=10, max=60), with 28.9% of participants classified as having smartphone addiction. The mean total score of the Satisfaction with Life Scale was 15.6 ± 4.5 , indicating a moderate level of life satisfaction among participants. A significant difference was found between the frequency of checking the phone per day and the total SWLS score. Additionally, a significant relationship was observed between the hours spent on social media per day and the total SWLS score. Participants who perceived themselves as smartphone addicts had significantly lower SWLS scores. A significant and negative correlation was found between SWLS and SAS-SF scores ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Our study found a negative correlation between smartphone addiction and life satisfaction. As daily phone usage and time spent on social media increased, life satisfaction scores were observed to decline. Furthermore, individuals who perceived themselves as addicted to their phones exhibited lower levels of life satisfaction. These findings highlight the impact of smartphone usage habits on life satisfaction and underscore the importance of raising awareness on this issue.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Smartphone addiction, life satisfaction, social media

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Arslan, Y. (2016). An investigation on changing behaviours of university students switching from using classical cell phones to smartphones. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 4(6), 199–206.

Yusufoglu, O. S. (2017). Smartphones as a leisure activity and their effects on social life: A study on university students. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 6(5), 2414–2434.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Burcu Erdogan

Aydin Adnan Menderes University

School of Medicine

Department of Family Medicine

Aydin, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1334-1503>

burcudenizli@hotmail.com